

SMART AGRICULTURE AND IRRIGATION SYSTEM USING IOT TECHNOLOGY

Yathavi.T^{1*}, Soorya.R^{2*}, Arunagirish.B^{3*}, Gokul.R^{4*}, Shiranjeevi.A^{5*}

¹Assistant Professor, ECE Department, Coimbatore Institute of Technology, Coimbatore, India

^{2,3,4,5} UG Scholar, ECE Department, Coimbatore Institute of Technology, Coimbatore, India

***Corresponding Author**

E-Mail Id: yathavi@cit.edu.in

Abstract-Agriculture in India is livelihood for a majority of the population and It is the backbone of INDIA. A key aspect of this project is the integration of IoT based smart irrigation systems, which are designed to reduce manual labour and save farmers' time. Growing seasonal crops requires monitoring the environmental conditions to improve yields. The process involves checking the moisture, humidity, water level, and temperature of the land in cultivation in an automated manner. When irrigation is required, an automatic irrigation system is provided. Smart agriculture systems come with a variety of sensors that monitor the environment and provide sensed outputs to the controller. A message can be sent to farmers to provide them with the information they need. Terrace gardening can be done with this system even on a small scale. Every step and procedure in the system is carefully explained in a way that everyone can understand and follow.

Keywords : Arduino board, Soil moisture sensor, IR sensor, Humidity sensor, Temperature sensor, WIFI module etc.

I. INTRODUCTION

We read in the newspapers for many days about farmer's losses and farmers used to work out the soil maturity and suspicions for the production of yield. They won't worry about the temperature, water level and simply climate conditions that are terrible to farmers. The Internet of Things (IOT) is

reconstructing the agri-business which enables farmers to deal with challenges in the field, for example through the broad range of strategies, such as accuracy and practical farming. Through IOT, information about climate, humidity, temperature, and soil fertility can be gathered. An IOT-based examination can also identify wild plants, water levels, exact locations, field interruptions, field development, and horticulture practices. By using the Internet of Things, farmers are able to connect to their home from anywhere in the world. Remote sensors are used to track household conditions and smaller controls are used to control and mechanize the house shapes [1-11].

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

A portable wireless data logging system is included in this project for real-time process dynamics temperature control. Process variables (such as temperature, humidity, tilt, IR, fire, soil moisture) may change over time, and this has to be taken into account in order to control the variable at a fixed point. In this paper, a WiFi-interfaced temperature sensor node built with an 8-bit framework is presented. Within the range of the wireless temperature sensor, the sensing node transmits specific temperature variations to the central processing device. As data is collected and stored in the file, variations are tracked simultaneously at the central base

station. In this project, a 32-bit embedded microcontroller-based wireless data logging system is designed and developed. The proposed system has the following main functions:

- Temperature, humidity, tree and water monitoring on a spontaneous basis
- Using a wifi module to transfer data over the internet to a server
- Configuring each module to operate as a sensing node can enable peer-to-peer networking and multipoint networking.

III. PROPOSED SYSTEM

To improve the quality of our crop, we must use technologies that analyze the essence of the harvest and provide advice to both farmers and government officials. With the Internet of Things (IOT), farmers are able to engage in a broad variety of techniques for going up against challenges in the field, such as accuracy and conservative cultivation. In precision agriculture, wireless sensor networks are used. By evaluating various differentiating factors for location and yield, this report offers a significant benefit. A precision agriculture system emphasizes both precision in the product territories and precision in the transportation of soil, fertilizer, etc. In this invention, a single plant is isolated in ten square meters or more for testing. Agriculturally exacting farming requires a novel programming model for each land area, the soil characteristics, and the particular harvests and crops. There will be a specific amount of water, compost, and pesticide in every area. Generally, hourly data collection is recommended. In addition to providing no extra helpful data for the display, visitor information collection turns the wireless sensor network into a weight for power consumption and data transmission. It might be sufficient to conduct fewer

ongoing studies in regions with highly stable and uniform climates and moderate harvests.

The working is as follows.

- With a wifi communication module, each sensor network will continuously update the parameter readings in the cloud.
- In the server room, changes in data that may trigger alarms will also be recorded and notified.
- Data and warning notifications can be accessed by local authorities or the concerned authorities.
- It is possible to analyze fields based on the data stored in a cloud called ThingSpeak server.

A. SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

Using valuable and realistic technology to monitor big machines and tech devices will help a farmer better understand how they work. The project uses various sensors to prevent this smuggling, including tilt sensors, flame sensors, soil moisture sensors, temperature sensors, and humidity sensors and WiFi is also used for communication purposes. A new method has been introduced to prevent the cutting down of trees in this proposed system using a server called ThinkSpeak. A tilt sensor determines whether the tree has been cut down, as does a temperature sensor determine if there is a fire in the field. Infrared sensors are used to detect objects; moisture sensors are placed in fields to monitor soil moisture content and relay switches activate based on their behavior. Through the use of the Thinkview application, this value will be constantly sent to the cloud through WiFi, where it can be accessed.

Fig.1: Smart Agriculture System

B. WORKFLOW DIAGRAM

As shown in Figure 1, the data received from the multiple sensors are compared and verified to the threshold values and the field is irrigated when the values are below the threshold values. The values are generated in the application by sending it to the cloud using ESP8266 and the farmer can get a look at the current status of his field.

IV. IMPLEMENTATION

Step1: To upload the code to Arduino board, we first write the code in Arduino IDE. As the sensors transmit data, Arduino sends it to the Thing Speak server in the cloud.

Step2: The Arduino board is used to connect the sensors, the wifi module, the relay switch, the led, and the buzzer.

Step3: This cable is used to provide the voltage necessary to run the Arduino board and to view the serial output on the board

Fig.2: Flow Diagram of the Proposed System

when connected to an IDE (Integrated Development Environment).

Step 4: Using the Arduino IDE, the data is uploaded to Arduino hardware.

Step 5: Once the Arduino board is activated, the following functions are implemented based on the behaviour of the sensor Temperature and humidity sensor: immediately after the board has been activated, it will show the exact temperature and humidity at that particular location. Temperature and humidity can be detected with the help of this sensor. Fig.3 shows the DHT11 sensor.

DHT11 Sensor: This sensor is essentially a low-cost digital temperature and humidity sensor. This sensor supplies digital output

and therefore can be directly connected to data pins of microcontroller in spite of using ADC. Additionally, it has an eight-bit microcontroller that can output serial data that represents temperature and humidity levels. There are four pins on it: VCC, GND, DATA, and NC. The power supply for this device is 3.3-5 volts. This sensor offers high quality, interference resistance, economic performance, and advantages for quick responses. It can measure the humidity ranging from 20-90% RH and measures temperature from 0-50 C. It also has a good accuracy with 5% RH and also it can be interchangeable. The function called read () is used to take readings from the sensor which is included in library.

Fig.3: DHT11 sensor

L293D Motor Driver- An integrated circuit chip known as a motor driver is typically used to operate motors in autonomous robots. An Arduino and the motors are connected by a motor driver. The L293 series of ICs, including the L293D, L293NE, and others, are the most often used motor driver ICs. These ICs are designed to control two DC motors simultaneously. L293D consist of two H- bridge. The simplest circuit for managing a motor with a low current rating is an H-bridge. The motor driver IC will just be referred to as L293D. 16 pins make up L293D. The L293D is a 16 pin IC having eight motor control pins on each side of the chip. Each motor has a total of four pins: two inputs, two outputs, and one enable pin. There are two H-bridges in L293D. An H-bridge circuit is the simplest

way to control a motor with a low current rating.

Fig.4: Relay

A relay-it is a device that switches. Many relays that mechanically control switches use electromagnets, although other fundamentals can also be used, such as solid-state relays. Relays are employed when it is crucial to operate a circuit with just one signal. Relay therefore functions as an automatic switch that switches a low current signal on a high current circuit. Here, dual channel 5V relay is used shown in the Fig.4.

Motor- Fig.5 is a micro submersible pump which works on DC 3 to 6v with cost efficient and portable. It is able to take around 120 litres for every hour with extremely low current utilization. The water level should be higher because overheated parts of this device could be damaged if the motor is utilised without water. Numerous applications exist, including hydroponic systems, controlled garden watering systems, and controlled fountain water flow.

Fig.5: Motor

Soil Moisture Sensor- Fig.6 One type of sensor used to determine the volumetric content of water in the soil is the soil moisture sensor. Because sample weighting,

drying, and elimination of the straight gravimetric dimension of soil moisture are required. Electrical resistance, neutron interactions, dielectric constants, and other soil laws are used to measure volumetric water content indirectly through these sensors. The relationship between the computed property and soil moisture needs to be changed and could alter depending on environmental conditions like temperature, soil type, or electric conductivity. The moisture of the soil can have an impact on the reflected microwave emission, which is mostly used in hydrology and agriculture.

Capacitance is primarily used by this sensor to measure the soil's moisture content (dielectric permittivity). This sensor can function by being inserted into the ground, and the status of the water content in the soil can be provided as a percentage. The use of this sensor makes it ideal for experiments in science classes covering topics in horticulture, biology, soil science,

Fig.5: Soil Moisture Sensor agriculture, environmental science, and more.

Moisture sensors have the following applications:

- Agriculture
- Landscape irrigation
- Research
- Land mine
- Simple sensors for gardeners

V. RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

All the sensors and hardware components which are interconnected to each other.

Fig.6: Sensors Connected to Hardware

Fig.6 implies the moisture content is less than 40% and shows that the field has to be irrigated.

Fig.7: Hardware Setup

Fig.7 shows the entire hardware setup of the proposed system.

Fig.8: Server output when soil moisture is less than 40%

Conference on System, Computation,
Automation and Networking
(ICSCAN),2019.

DOI: 10.1109/ICSCAN.2019.8878685.

[8] T. Yathavi,Ajay. R.,Hariesh Varshan
R.P.,John Timothy J,“Development of Auto
Tracking and Target Fixing Gun using
Machine Vision” in IEEE International
Conference on System, Computation,
Automation and Networking (ICSCAN).
2020.

DOI: 0.1109/ICSCAN49426.2020.9262451